

D3.2 Deployment of the VITIGEOSS cloud-based application portal

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Executive summary

This document addresses the developments and deployment phase of the VitiGEOSS cloud-based application portal and informs on deliverable 3.2, which is a demonstrator. Section 1 presents the solution and architecture describing the functionality of each of the components for the visualisation and exchange of the information among partners in VitiGEOSS. Section 2 presents a set of mock-ups describing both the Application and API Service Store. They serve as guideline to describe the features co-designed with the end-users and intelligent service providers to present the different services and functionality for authenticating the APIs. A preliminary set of standards are defined to facilitate the exchange of information, which will be addressed and further elaborated when configuring the intelligent services into the VitiGEOSS application. Section 3 presents a functional demonstrator, based on FieldLook, to access and visualise the information for one of the end-users. Also, the functionality of API Service store is demonstrated with APIs provided by the intelligent service providers. Section 4 summarises the actions to be developed with the project partners including the implementation of the VitiGEOSS layout and configuration of the intelligent services and functional tests. These actions will be coordinated and reported accordingly as part of the project in other deliverables.

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List of abbreviations

<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicators</i>
<i>NDVI</i>	<i>Normalised Difference Vegetation Index</i>
<i>SSOT</i>	<i>Single Source Of Truth</i>
<i>STS</i>	<i>Security Token Service</i>

1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the deployment of the VitiGEOSS cloud-based application portal. It presents a description of the portal and the interaction among the different components and architecture based on the intelligent service requirements. The results include a functional and working demo of the VitiGEOSS application for the pilot plots defined in the project.

This document builds on the system architecture, which is described in the System Architecture blueprint deliverable (D3.9) [1], and definition of the use case scenarios describing the technical configuration of the different use cases and mock-ups for the intelligent services, which are reported on the use case scenarios descriptions (D3.1)[2]. During the formulation of these two deliverables some modifications were proposed to the system architecture. These modifications are based on the intelligent service requirements and used as guideline to structure the implementation of the VitiGEOSS application portal, which are reported in section 1. Section 2 presents the different components of the VitiGEOSS application. Section 3 presents a demonstration of the API service store and VitiGEOSS application accessing and visualising the information. And section 4 presents the further developments proposed for the implementation of the platform.

1.1 VitiGEOSS cloud solution

VitiGEOSS cloud solution is composed by Fieldlook and VISCA technologies, among other technologies improved during the project, to increase resolution and reliability of earth observation information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations. Five unique intelligent services will be developed to address specific aspects of the vineyard management.

Weather/climate forecasting

This service will demonstrate the potential application of probabilistic sub-seasonal and seasonal climate prediction in combination with meteorological short-term forecast. These forecasts will inform wine producers about the climatic conditions for the next weeks and months with respect to historical conditions at each site, as well as prepare in advance to extreme events.

Phenology

Prediction and monitoring of phenological stages will provide viticulturist with important strategic information that will help them in better planning and organising the whole vineyard management.

Crop status

Key crop parameters on Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), biomass production, evapotranspiration and nitrogen will be produced throughout the growing season at regular intervals for all the fields in the pilot project. This information will be used to generate management zones and optimise yield forecast which will help wine producers to monitor crop development and plan management practices.

Diseases management

Downy mildew and powdery mildew risk will be forecasted in order prevent the diseases effects by giving to farmers the needed information beforehand. In addition, recipes against the diseases will be recommended and scheduled promoting sustainable practices reducing the number of pesticides used when possible.

Business and sustainability

Two services will empower the improvement of business and sustainability indicators by end-users. A resource optimiser and planner service will help improving field management activities, planning of resources, and reducing the use of agricultural inputs, which will result in an improvement of the revenues and business operations for the wine industry. The second service, a sustainability manager, will allow the evaluation of production standards based on the analysis of sustainability indicators targeting productivity, environmental protection, and economic viability.

The aforementioned intelligent services will be configured and deployed in the VitiGEOSS portal, including API Service Store, VitiGEOSS application and Access manager.

1.2 Modifications based on intelligent service requirements

From the onset of the project, it was evident that the architecture of VitiGEOSS portal needed to be redesigned based on the intelligent service requirements. The original proposition to host standalone applications for individual intelligent services was analysed and after evaluating different options, the consortium decided to take advantage of an already existing commercial tool, Fieldlook, to unify the user interface of the intelligent services and thus improve the user's experience and ways of work and future commercialisation.

Fieldlook is eLEAF's state of the art platform which is used for the visualisation of both crop status and crop water demand. Fieldlook has gradually evolved in a powerful web portal supporting satellite derived information on single fields up to entire river basins. In the Western Cape of South Africa, Fruitlook, an instantiation of Fieldlook, supports wine grapes and other fruit farmers to enhance on-farm resources and crop management. Fieldlook has been used to support the crop monitoring of wine grapes, fruits, cereals and sugarcane in North and South America, Africa and Asia. Therefore, it was decided to use Fieldlook for the integration of all VitiGEOSS intelligent services from the beginning offering thus, a commercial tool for farmers to increase the marketable potential of VitiGEOSS.

The results of previous research project VISCA¹ will be reused to support the VitiGEOSS services. VISCA phenology component will be adopted as a basis for developing new phenology monitoring and forecasting models and VISCA sensor service component will be adapted to support the in-field repository of VitiGEOSS weather data. Both the components will expose data to end-users and intelligent service providers through the API Service Store and VitiGEOSS application.

1.3 VitiGEOSS architecture

The VitiGEOSS portal has three distinctive components, the API Service Store (light blue) for service providers, the VitiGEOSS application for the end-users (dark blue) and the Access Manager (green) **Error! Reference source not found.**

¹ VISCA -<https://www.visca.eu/>

Figure 1. VitiGELOSS Portal Architecture

VitiGELOSS Application

The VitiGELOSS application represents the user interface available on a public website. This represents a single Sign On system to visualise all the intelligent services. It is based on an instantiation of eLEAF’s Fieldlook Progressive Web Application and will evolve into VitiGELOSS application embracing new functionalities developed in the project by all intelligent services. This will result in a highly intuitive application available to the end-user 24/7 with updated information derived from the intelligent services at field level during the project cycle.

The VitiGELOSS application involves the migration of Fieldlook Progressive Web Application from a Joomla Framework into Laravel Framework for the modularity, co-development and the flexibility needed in the VitiGELOSS project. This includes upload of base code, testing of environment, customisation of modules used to present and support field information and adoption of VitiGELOSS layout for supporting a recognised visual identity within VitiGELOSS project material and social media.

Access manager

The access manager is responsible for the security with the components API Configurator and User/ID Management. The access manager will be managed through the VitiGEOSS application and API Service Store. Data from and to VitiGEOSS Intelligent services or other third-party data providers will be managed (authorised and authenticated) in the API service Store. In the VitiGEOSS Application the component of the Access Manager, User/ID Management will be responsible to authorise and give access to end-user when accessing the application. Both components of the access manager (embedded in the VitiGEOSS application and API Service Store) work together in handling data requests and responses from VitiGEOSS application encapsulated in API-Service Store.

API service store

The API service store forms a repository of consortium intelligent services and enables the connection of these data-services to the VitiGEOSS application available to the end-user. It encompasses the data service repository, metadata management and API manager to form a repository of intelligent services, which will enable the connection between these data services and the VitiGEOSS application available to the end-users on a public web-site (green tile). The API Manager will provide features for managing and monitoring the APIs that will be connected through the service. This component is realised in an OpenAPI environment facilitating thus the configuration and integration with the APIs planned for supporting the intelligent services. The OpenAPI Specification (OAS) defines a standard, language-agnostic interface to RESTful APIs.

These components are described in detail in the section below.

2. VitiGEOSS portal

A simplified functional block architecture of the modified VitiGEOSS Portal is presented in Figure . In this figure the intelligent services data production is presented in the left and the users of the application in the right. In the middle a functional block architecture (purple box) contains the components of the portal, presented as:

- i) the access manager responsible for the security with components API Configurator and User/ID Management.
- ii) the VitiGEOSS application as the user interface supported by Fieldlook features.
- iii) The API Configurator within the API Service Store enables the connection, and the ID manager enables authorization/authentication for the VitiGEOSS application to the intelligent services by any user supported with the API Management and Metadata Management. The data flow is depicted in orange. The arrows flow from the VITIGE OSS application to the intelligent services and from the VitiGEOSS application users to the intelligent services.

Figure 2. Functional VitiGEOSS Portal Architecture

2.1 VitiGEOSS application

In the VitiGEOSS application two instances are hosted: VitiGEOSS production, VitiGEOSS acceptance (for testing). These two instances will have similar functionalities.

VitiGEOSS **production** will be running operational for the end-users in an automated environment providing access to the intelligent service information in the right frequency as defined by the nature of the intelligent services.

VitiGEOSS **acceptance** is a test environment that will offer the possibility to test and demonstrate the functionality of new features to end-users or intelligent services providers (using also their acceptance versions) before they are deployed into the production environment. This functionality is very useful in the development of long-term projects such as VitiGEOSS because it facilitates the development and test of new functionalities without corrupting the operational environment and thus interaction with the end-users.

VitiGEOSS application will evolve from the FieldLook application into an application that will embrace the new functionalities developed in the project by all the intelligent service providers. They will result from the combination of current features of existing Fieldlook field management capabilities and a co-design approach involving end-users and intelligent service providers to collect user requirements and assess its feasibility and implement when possible into the VitiGEOSS application.

The VitiGEOSS application (<https://www.vitigeoss.com>) will use a dedicated web-domain setup for the wine producers in the project to access the application. The numerical values, dates and imagery intelligent services are retrieved through the API Service Store and sent to the VitiGEOSS application. Currently this component uses FieldLook solution that provides a Progressive Web Application in the form of the HTML+Javascript+CSS code that will be uploaded into the end-users browser.

Orders are handled through php and Javascript, while services will be accessible calling APIs. This is where the end-user order information (such as field geometries) is sent back to delivery and stored by the Client's application into values database, for further use and processing.

The service worker contains services in Javascript giving the possibility to run additional scripts in the background.

The webserver for VitiGEOSS is working with Docker containers in Pods (images are available in Docker Hubs) with Laravel installation. Containers provide maximum of flexibility and working speed to manage the IT infrastructure for the VitiGEOSS project.

Following two co-design general meetings on 21 December 2020 and on 26 May 2021, which involved end-users and intelligent service provides, a set of mock-ups were designed for the functionality and visualisation of the different intelligent services as summarised below.

2.1.1 Weather and climate service

This service consists of three types of forecasts, short-term forecast, sub seasonal predictions and seasonal predictions. The weather or short-term forecasts will be visualised as a time evolution for the selected surface variables along the x-axis. The y-axis will indicate the magnitude of the chosen variable. The display will consist of bars or lines and the timesteps are 3-hourly up to 3 days into the future. In the case of climate predictions (sub seasonal and seasonal timescales) a different approach has been followed to accommodate the probabilistic nature of this type of predictions, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** **Error! Reference source not found.** The end-user will have the possibility to select the climate parameter to be displayed. The output of forecasted models will be displayed with coloured bars indicating probabilities below normal, normal and above normal. The y-axis will indicate the probability of each tercile category. Low/high extremes will be shown when there is a probability of 40% and greater of occurrence. Additional features like presenting the information while hovering above the bars or shading probabilities when the skill is below 0% will be supported.

Figure 3. Visualisation intelligent service for climate predictions (sub seasonal and seasonal).

2.1.2 Phenology service

The service consists in providing information about the phenological stage of the management unit. The phenology service will provide the results of monitoring and forecasting models based different data sources (remote sensing, weather station, cameras). The service will be supported with a separate page where the end-user can visualise the parameters to model crop phenology. **Error! Reference source not found.** presents a view of the service, which shows for a defined management unit the information about the predicted date, the detected date, and the achieved date per phenological stage. The user will have the possibility to choose the data source and the model from which obtain the information for detection and forecast of the phenological stage. The end users have the possibility to provide the actual dates (achieved dates) in which phenology stages change occurs. This information will allow the realignment of the phenology prediction and monitoring models. This page will also include a description of the phenological stages with image samples according to Baggiolini scale. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a second view presenting aggregated information according to the user selection for the different models used to estimate the phenological dates.

Figure 4. Visualisation phenology service per management unit.

Figure 5. Visualisation output of phenological models.

2.1.3 Crop status service

The key crop indicator tracking service will be supported with the current functionality of Fieldlook presenting a service to monitor crop development and water use variables on a weekly basis. Figure shows time series of the development of different management units. This allows the comparison per crop indicator throughout the growing season. Maps insets can present a spatial overview depicting areas with good/poor performance. In addition, spatial metrics including maximum, minimum, average and deviation are summarised to evaluate the heterogeneity of the management units.

Figure 6. Visualisation of crop developing variable, and map inset.

Figure presents a table layout displaying the statistics of all key crop indicators for all management units. This feature is supported with a colour code to set the performance and allow comparisons among different management units.

Field	Crop	Nitrogen (kg/ha)			Biomass production (kg/ha)			ET (mm/week)			NDVI {}		
		Wk 15	Wk 16	Wk 17	Wk 15	Wk 16	Wk 17	Wk 15	Wk 16	Wk 17	Wk 15	Wk 16	Wk 17
Bon1	Peach	16.90	20.08	14.48	635	705	597	0.19	0.12	0.16	0.00	0.54	0.00
Bon2	Peach	18.57	21.24	14.72	913	972	771	0.25	0.27	0.27	0.00	0.70	0.00
For-XP1	Pear	17.25	19.44	13.79	860	936	745	0.59	0.20	0.61	0.00	0.66	0.00
For-XP12	Pear	19.21	21.85	15.31	746	788	637	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.00	0.58	0.00
For-XP13	Pear	11.23	12.89	8.86	634	655	544	0.46	0.42	0.42	0.00	0.53	0.00
For-XP2	Pear	19.98	23.13	16.20	817	891	716	0.13	0.10	0.13	0.00	0.64	0.00
For-XP3	Pear	18.47	21.37	14.97	699	760	615	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.58	0.00
For-XP4	Pear	20.10	23.05	16.02	885	950	751	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.00	0.69	0.00
For-XP5	Pear	17.43	19.78	13.73	658	694	552	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.00	0.53	0.00
GD-BO1	Apple	14.91	17.72	10.67	1002	1027	698	0.31	0.14	0.31	0.00	0.64	0.00
GD-BO10	Apple	17.61	21.54	14.10	767	851	643	0.27	0.10	0.46	0.00	0.58	0.00
GD-BO11	Apple	15.90	19.60	12.39	675	747	538	0.19	0.13	0.21	0.00	0.53	0.00
GD-BO12	Apple	20.83	24.15	16.00	1135	1182	877	0.50	0.10	0.50	0.00	0.73	0.00
GD-BO13	Apple	22.28	26.00	17.31	1097	1156	869	0.66	0.10	0.66	0.00	0.72	0.00
GD-BO14	Apple	22.97	26.26	17.32	1133	1162	859	0.66	0.10	0.66	0.00	0.72	0.00
GD-BO15	Apple	22.40	25.91	16.88	1126	1164	862	0.70	0.10	0.70	0.00	0.72	0.00
Min		7.76	10.17	6.28	342	425	334	0.08	0.10	0.08	0.00	0.41	0.00
Average		18.05	21.16	14.02	817	862	653	0.28	0.13	0.22	0.00	0.64	0.00
Max		23.07	26.26	18.53	1151	1182	877	1.72	0.47	0.70	0.00	0.78	0.00

Figure 7. Visualisation of crop field statistics.

2.1.4 Disease management service

This service will support the risks and probabilities of appearance of downy mildew and powdery mildew, two particular diseases in grapes. Figure presents a dashboard with the risk of the disease per management unit at daily intervals and probability of the disease in weekly intervals. It is proposed to use a visual response of the treatments based on predefined recipes. In addition, the user will be notified when a high risk of the disease is forecasted in the list presenting all the management units implemented in the pilot.

Figure 8. Visualisation of the risk and probability of downy mildew and powdery mildew.

2.1.5 Business and sustainability services

The business and sustainability services will present the possibility to end-users for planning their management operations in a flexible calendar allowing the modification of activities throughout the growing season. Predefined resources could be visualised and reallocated based on the day-to-day operations. Figure 2 shows an example of allocating trucks (for transport) and workers (needed to do the tasks) for activities related with harvesting practices.

Figure 2. Visualisation of activity planner.

The sustainability service will be used to report on key performance indicators (KPIs). The KPIs would need to be updated by end-users at different time intervals based on the definition of the indicator. Figure 1 presents the mock-up for the sustainability service. A set of predefined KPIs will be presented with the metrics for each indicator. This service will be open for end-user's feedback and for monitoring the development of the indicators throughout the growing season.

Figure 30. Visualisation sustainability indicators.

2.2 API Service Store

The API Service Store is a component that manages services in APIs and provides an extra interface for partners to register APIs. It manages access control, authentication, authorization of services, of data, users of the API service store and eventually users of the VITIGE OSS application.

It provides a friendly user interface where partners can register their APIs that handle all kinds of (data) requests from and to intelligent services to provide to the end users of the VitiGEOSS application.

The API Service Store is composed of the following components:

- Data service repository “**API Manager**”, Figure 4, with an extra interface for Partners (“**Publisher**” and “**Devportal**”) to add, manage and control all APIs created.
- Authentication/Authorization application and API configurator, *Figure 5*: “**Identity Server**”- manages all authorization/authentication/access control of services, of data, of users/partners in the API store (and eventually of end users of the VITIGE OSS application. All of this is mainly managed in WSO2 Identity server’s key manager. In the WSO2 publisher/devportal management part you can choose what authorization to use for the specific API in the runtime config (authentication methods need to be specified in the identity server’s key manager by an admin)

Figure 41. API Service Store - Publisher

Figure 52. API Service Store - Identity Server.

2.2.1 Data service repository

This is the repository of services/APIs that are exposed by partners. APIs are described with the state-of-the-art metadata and will be discussed and defined in close collaboration with the intelligent services providers to allow easy collaboration and composition of the services.

The API Service Store supports OpenAPI Specification (Swagger) version 3.0, using microgateway. The swagger 2.0 specifies the combination of schemes, with these, basePath and host attributes, microgateway will drive the back-end service url using host and schemes, and drive the base path using the base path attribute. The open API 3.0 specification defines a way of providing a server url of the API defined by the open API definition. Microgateway drive the base path and the back-end service url using the servers object defined in the open API definition. For: `http://fieldlooktest.com/serv` then microgateway will resolve backend service url as the given URL and it will also expose the API using the base path(context) `/serv`.

OpenAPI doesn't specify all required properties. It's meant to be a descriptor of a REST endpoint. That is the OpenAPI definition of a backend endpoint. To define different types of endpoints, gateway security, rate limiting and/or other gateway specific features per API or per resource. Since Microgateway is using the OpenAPI definition as the SSOT (Single Source Of Truth). These additional properties go into OpenAPI definition maintained inside a microgateway project. Microgateway utilizes OpenAPI Specification's vendor extensions for this purpose.

2.2.2 API Manager

API Manager, provides enterprises with features for creating, managing, consuming, and monitoring APIs. It also helps to address a breadth of API challenges, including governance, monitoring, security and provisioning. WSO2 API Manager comes with an API Designer and Publisher, a Developer Portal, an API Gateway, and API analytics. Furthermore, it offers GraphQL support, AWS Lambda support, and a Kubernetes API Operator.

The API management is realised in an OpenAPI (Swagger) interface where a description of the service is found as presented with a contained instance of an API-manager in combination with an Identity Manager. The identity manager is used to authenticate and manage access control for users, data sources, services and APIs. This authentication allows end-users or service providers to use a single key for multiple APIs. The API Manager is used to redirect service request to the provided endpoints of the intelligent services APIs and controls and measures access to them. An access token is a simple string that is passed as an HTTP header of a request. Access tokens authenticate API users and applications ensuring better security (e.g., prevent certain types of DoS attacks). If a token that is passed with a request is invalid, the request is discarded at the first stage of processing.

2.2.3 Metadata management

The API Store Service will be based on Open API standards and specified further after evaluating the interaction with available semantic standards such as INSPIRE, Sare4Agri or taxonomies as defined in the VISCA project (<https://www.visca.eu/>). This was further addressed in the use case scenarios description document (D3.1) and will be closely specified in the development stages of the co-development of each intelligent service.

Currently a set of standards business entities are defined and discussed with intelligent service providers.

2.2.4 Standards services

An assessment of the available data standards carried out in D3.1 compiled the most relevant standards for Geographical Information Systems (GIS) data, Agriculture/Vineyard data, Machine and sensors data, sustainability data, disease data, risk management data and weather and climate data. As result of this review, it was stated that there is not only one standard valid

and therefore the most convenient for the project is the combination of different defined standards based on the defined data types.

The following standards were proposed for the main data types:

Geographical Information Systems (GIS) data

For the creation of new GIS data, it is proposed to follow the INSPIRE data models and requirements. Most of the GIS data created will be based on Copernicus raster images, so this requirement will be easily achieved. Regarding the management of spatial data from the end users, data is collected using ESRI standard format, i.e., shapefile, to collect the geometries of the vineyards of our end users also adding descriptive attributes to them.

Agricultural/Vineyard data

After a consensus between intelligent service providers and end-users, the data from end-users have been homogenised based on the vineyards characteristics that will be used in the project. Management unit naming, location, crop characteristics, soil types and irrigation systems were already defined and implemented to define each of the management units used in the pilot. Other agricultural data types include six phenological stages which are defined following the standards used in VISCA and key crop indicators derived from satellite imagery which will be defined following the standards used in FieldLook.

Machinery and sensor data

Data from tractors is expected to be collected from their CANBUS diagnostic port filtering relevant information by using CAN standard messages formats from J1939 standard. The standards of other sensors like fixed cameras, drone imagery, irrigation controllers to be used in the project will be analysed based on the standards defined and proposed in deliverable 3.1. Actual and historic weather data on solar radiation, air temperature, rainfall, air humidity, wind speed, wind direction and leaf wetness from meteorological stations is retrieved in xls and txt formats.

Sustainability data

WRI GHC Protocol² and ISO 14064³ will be proposed to consortium for the calculation of the CO₂ emissions. Other standards could be analysed in the following months to be incorporated into the project implementation once the sustainable components are defined.

Disease data and Risk management data

For forecasting the risk of downy and powdery mildew for the next days, weeks or months for the selected management units, it is proposed to analyse the document ISPM 2⁴ Framework for pest analysis and also the data models defined in the Smart Data Models initiative⁵.

Weather and Climate data

The climate data files are stored in netCDF files and follow the CF and INSPIRE conventions. The weather data follow NCEP convention. To homogenise the variable names throughout the weather and climate data, NCEP naming convention will be applied also to the climate predictions. The metadata is compliant with CF conventions.

The aforementioned standards will be further discussed with the intelligent service providers to facilitate and homogenise process and data models for its visualisation in the VitiGEOSS application. As initial starting point the data concepts and models used in FieldLook and VISCA

² [Corporate Standard | Greenhouse Gas Protocol \(ghgprotocol.org\)](#)

³ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso:14064:-1:ed-2:v1:en>

⁴ <https://www.fao.org/3/k0125e/k0125e.pdf>

⁵ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.RiskManagement>

and concepts used by UNINA for the definition of the of the pilot plots and experience on semantic interoperability by Eurecat resulted in a well-defined set of attributes describing each of the management units provided in this project. Additionally, it was agreed that a single polygon in shape format will be used to define the boundaries of a management unit.

2.3 Access manager

Access management will be managed throughout the VitiGEOSS application and API Service Store. Data from and to VitiGEOSS intelligent services and other third-party data providers will be managed (authorized and authenticated) in the API Service Store. End goal is to get all VitiGEOSS data from Intelligent services into the VitiGEOSS application. In the VitiGEOSS application there is an access manager for end-users of the VitiGEOSS application, it manages authorization and authentication of users as well as access control of data using user profile rights.

1. Access Manager in VitiGEOSS Application - this is for the VitiGEOSS application users:
 - a. for authentication and authorization (login user/password/token user)
 - b. it combines users with their field data allowing end-users to visualise only their data of the current season or seasonal time series. (with their user profile rights)
 - c. it coordinates the routing of data to the API Service Store.
2. Access manager in API Service Store - “Identity Server” keystores for all API Service Store Users like intelligent services, partners and developers:
 - a. authentication and authorization (login API store user/password, delivering/managing tokens, endpoints, user profiles) STS Security Token Service
 - b. Access control (restrict access to resources/services by entitlement policies and rules), will all be managed in the API service Store (Identity Server).

Both Access managers (VitiGEOSS application and API Service Store) work together in handling data requests and responses from VitiGEOSS application users encapsulated in the API-Service Store.

2.3.1 Access manager VitiGEOSS application

The access management for the VitiGEOSS application (vitigeoss/fieldlook) is taken over from Fieldlook. Currently this is based on Joomla for credential and role management. Access management has multiple levels: access to the application (login, security tokens, sessions etc.), roles (e.g. farmer, consultant) which define the available views in vitigeoss/fieldlook and access to data that the user has the right to see (e.g. mapping of users to a farms), all of which are now fully integrated in the vitigeoss/fieldlook application. Work is ongoing to leverage the identity server (WSO2 identity server 5.11) in the API Service Store to provide this to vitigeoss/fieldlook in order to have a single place where users, credentials and roles are stored and managed.

Vitigeoss/fieldlook is built as a progressive web app (PWA) which stores most of the data in a browser-based database (IndexedDB). This reduces the amount of data needed to be downloaded each session and enables the user to work offline with the application. The application has the option to remove all stored data in order to leave a device 'clean' if needed (e.g. when using the application on a public or shared device).

2.3.2 Access manager API Service Store (Identity Server)

The Identity Server in the API Service Store handles user/id management and functions as API Configurator. It handles authorization and authentication for different user types. It coordinates the routing of data to the API Service Store. It is a WSO2 system that is in a separate

environment, installed with containers technology. This WSO2 API service Store contains a API Identity Server with a keystore. With this advanced technology all authentication authorization, access control requirements of the VITIGE OSS application can be met and managed. User types to access API Service Store can be defined as:

- Intelligent services
- VITIGE OSS Application (encapsulated)
- VITIGE OSS Developers
- Third party user interfaces
- Third party services
- Admin

Authentication and authorization, access control (restrict access to a resource by entitlement policies and -rules), STS Security Token Service, will all be managed in the API service Store (Identity Server). The identity server has the option to provide authentication using external providers using several authentication protocols (e.g., SAML 2.0, OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0 and WS-Trust). This means that a partner can provide access to data via the API service store using its own user management/authentication system.

The Identity Server's API configurator maps data requests to the configured partner APIs. Mapping is done at end user level so different end users can use different API providers to get the same data components. For instance, an end-user in Portugal might use a Portuguese meteorological data provider for temperature while a Spanish end-user might use a Spanish provider. Or they might use the same provider but different APIs (weekly averages instead of daily averages).

The **Identity Server** contains a keystore where tokens can be specified in WSO2 API Manager. There are three different types of keystores available:

Primary Keystore - used for signing and encryption for the data which is externally exposed. Example use cases are signing SAML response, OAuth ID Token Signing and signing JWTs.

Secondary Keystore (TLS Connections) - used for authenticating communication over SSL/TLS. This is used in various transports used by WSO2 API Manager including servlet transport (used for webapps), Synapse transport (used in gateway), thrift, binary and JMS.

Internal Keystore used for encrypting internal critical data including passwords and other confidential information in configuration files.

3. Demonstration API Service Store and Application

As mentioned in section 1.1, VitiGEOSS solution intends to combine existing and novel technologies to increase the resolution and reliability of earth observation information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations with the development of five unique intelligent services to address specific aspects of the vineyard management. In this section, we present a step-by-step guidance on how intelligent services can access the API Service Store and how end-users can access the FieldLook application. The latter will evolve into the VitiGEOSS application including all intelligent services to accomplish the intended functionalities presented in section 2.1. The API Service Store establishes the connection with individual service providers aiming to sharing data and services between partners and publishing of the services through the VitiGEOSS application.

3.1 API Service Store

The demo of the API Service Store shows how intelligent service providers, or third parties can access and publish their APIs in the API Service Store. This environment is meant by VitiGEOSS developers and administrators. The Admin Portal is strictly managed by the administrator, who manages the API Service Store, assigns roles and manages the data base and security. An overview of the components and interfaces of the API Service Store to be used by the VitiGEOSS developers such as the Publisher interface and Developer portal, and Admin Portal to be used and managed by eLEAF are presented below.

3.1.1 Publisher interface

In order to access the publisher environment user and password are requested as presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Publisher log in page (API Service Store).

Once access is granted, the VitiGEOSS developer can access authorised APIs as presented in Figure, where the developer can access APIs of the different intelligent service provides or create a new API based on existing ones.

Figure 14. List of APIs available by the developer.

After the creation of the API, developers can publish in the API Service Store and visualise the created API in the publisher as presented in Figure . The configuration of the API can be visualised with a set of attributes in the left panel.

Figure 15. Publisher configurator of the service.

3.1.2 Developer portal

In this environment developers can test and document their own API and subscribed APIs. Figure 16 presents the developer interface where the different APIs are available. The developer can test the available APIs to check that the functionalities and behaviour are correctly met.

Figure 16. Developer interface.

The testing environment in Figure 16 shows the necessary attributes to pull meteorological data from the API of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, intelligent service provider.

Figure 16. Testing environment for the API of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

3.1.3 Admin portal

The Admin portal will be managed and used by eLEAF, eLEAF will manage the API Service Store, assign roles, create permissions, manage databases and security. Figure 17 presents the dashboard of the Admin portal, describing the subscribed APIs and Figure 18 presents the identity server where the authorisation and authentication are configured for the intelligent service providers.

Figure 17. Admin portal - API Service Store

Figure 18. Authentication and authorisation configuration for the intelligent service providers.

3.2 VitiGEOSS Application

VitiGEOSS application will be available via the web browser (www.vitigeoss.com) after the migration of the key crop indicators available in FieldLook sandbox (<https://fieldlook.com/sandbox/index.php/en/>). The current sandbox environment offers the possibility to demonstrate the functionality of the application to end-users before the VitiGEOSS application is launched with all the intelligent services. The FieldLook sandbox supports the functionality of the key crop indicators of VitiGEOSS service until the web application is fully migrated into Laravel framework. Once this process is completed, the configuration of other intelligent services will begin.

The end-user can navigate to <https://fieldlook.com/sandbox/index.php/en/> and fill in the authentication form with the authorised username and password, as shown in Figure 20 in order to log in to the tool.

Figure 9. FieldLook log in page.

In case of wrong credentials, the platform will notify the user accordingly (Figure 21). After the successful login, the user will be redirected to the landing page of FieldLook (Figure 22). The option forgot username and forgot your password are available to resend the username and reset the password.

Figure 10. The FieldLook response to invalid credentials during the log in progress.

Figure 11. Landing page of FieldLook after successful login.

3.2.1 Exploring management units

From the menu bar, the end-user can select the “Farm” to connect in the Farm selection menu item in order to navigate to the full list of Farms available per company as displayed in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Farm selection menu item to navigate through the list of farms.

In the left side of the application different tabs facilitate the selection of seasons, crops and present general information. The filter tab (Figure 24A) offers a quick selection of crops, season and other variables, which will reduce the selection of the management units, farms and varieties of interest. The Workset tab (Figure 24B) shows the set of fields in the active selection, only for the season and crop of interest. The selected fields turn green and stay highlighted in other views. The passport tab (Figure 24C) presents ancillary field information per management unit.

Figure 13. Selection tabs Filter, Workset and Passport.

3.2.2 Exploring analysis between management units

Two types of analysis for the management units are available: Map and Analyse in the upper tabs.

Map

The Map tab presents an aerial view of the current selection. A predefined benchmark presents via an easy colour code. Fields coloured RED indicate below average performance of the specific data component and fields coloured YELLOW indicate average performance as depicted in Figure 14. Fields coloured GREEN indicate above average performance.

Figure 14. Map analysis of management units.

The Analyse view change the view of the selected data and fields for analysis. Four types of analysis are available: graph, single field, statistics and overview.

Graph

The graph view, time series show the development of the management units over the season (Figure 26). It allows you to compare fields through time. The graph display can change with the selection of the different key crop parameters. The management units can be selected and deselected in order to facilitate comparisons among fields. Insets of the spatial information can be selected at different time intervals to depict spatial differences between fields as depicted in Figure 16.

Figure 15. Graph of biomass production for management units of Quinta do Bomfim.

Figure 16. Graph of evapotranspiration and insets of week 16 and week 21 for management unit BF 257.

Single field

Single field gives both the graphical, Figure 17, and spatial overview, Figure 18, of all key crop parameters per management unit. It is perfect for a detailed analysis of the management units and identifying the most limiting parameter during the growing season or at a particular interval. The possibility to display graphs and spatial components in one single functionality facilitates the analysis and monitoring of management practices.

Figure 17. Graphical presentation of Biomass production, Evapotranspiration, Potential evapotranspiration and NDVI.

Figure 18. Overview of the biomass production, evapotranspiration, potential evapotranspiration and NDVI.

Statistics

Statistical analysis displays the average status of all management units as depicted in Figure 19. This viewer summarises all management units and key crop indicators per week of analysis. The system uses the same colour convention as define in the benchmark to identify over and underperforming management units. Underperforming management units are coloured red and overperforming management unit coloured green.

Field	Crop	Biomass production (kg/ha)			Evapotranspiration (mm/week)			NDVI			Potential evapotranspiration (mm/week)		
		Wk 26	Wk 27	Wk 28	Wk 26	Wk 27	Wk 28	Wk 26	Wk 27	Wk 28	Wk 26	Wk 27	Wk 28
BF 105	grape	493	437	560	11.60	10.16	14.93	0.00	0.36	0.34	17.13	14.47	17.06
BF 255_B	grape	389	349	251	7.89	7.29	8.72	0.00	0.23	0.22	11.34	9.60	9.64
BF 255_C	grape	756	545	762	14.36	10.68	17.53	0.00	0.43	0.40	17.98	13.58	19.32
BF 255_V	grape	577	475	611	11.24	9.41	14.78	0.00	0.37	0.35	15.93	12.71	16.44
BF 256	grape	775	560	531	14.43	10.85	13.30	0.00	0.35	0.32	16.62	13.17	14.84
BF 257	grape	601	473	704	11.53	9.46	16.44	0.00	0.40	0.37	13.67	11.61	18.00
Min		389	349	251	7.89	7.29	8.72	0.00	0.23	0.22	11.34	9.60	9.64
Average		621	490	598	12.17	9.89	14.75	0.00	0.37	0.34	15.65	12.72	16.34
Max		775	592	770	14.43	11.35	17.53	0.00	0.43	0.40	17.98	14.47	19.32

Figure 19. Statistics of key crop indicators for the management units of Quinta do Bomfim.

Overview

The overview viewer shows in-field variation per key crop indicator for the group of management units per farm of interest as depicted in Figure 20. The spatial variation per key crop indicator can look stable from week to week. This variation can change on a weekly basis and therefore, end-users can highlight insets during the growing season allowing for the comparisons between management units to monitor the development of management practices.

Figure 20. Overview of evapotranspiration for the management units of Quinta do Bomfim.

3.2.3 Downloading information

The information depicted in the workset can be downloaded in excel format to facilitate the interaction with the data in other platforms and sharing with other parties. This functionality generates a complete overview of the fields selected in the workset as depicted in Figure 21 and Figure 22. The information presented in the excel file is a collection of the active key crop indicators, coverage info and data components. Each key crop indicators is presented per excel sheet. In the header the weeks are organised per weeks and the first three columns present the management unit, crop type and management unit area. The coverage info excel sheet presents the management unit name, farm name, type of crop, variety, sowing date, harvest date and management unit area. The data components excel sheet presents the key crop indicators downloaded, units used and key crop indicator code.

Figure 21. Export functionality via excel format.

Field name	Crop	Area	2021-01	2021-02	2021-03	2021-04	2021-05	2021-06	2021-07	2021-08	2021-09	2021-10	2021-11	2021-12	2021-13	2021-14	2021-15	2021-16
BF 105	grape	2.08	80	87	92	90	237				511	405	399	340	261	228	277	
BF 255_B	grape	0.03		79	92	93	87	226			377	323	252	234	198	215	256	
BF 255_C	grape	0.24	140	154	154	145	377				503	438	410	474	380	483	530	
BF 255_V	grape	0.18	111	123	123	116	302				418	376	328	362	296	349	409	
BF 256	grape	0.28	145	158	159	150	390				567	467	472	497	391	492	547	
BF 257	grape	0.16	136	146	147	139	363				498	332	380	293	219	241	243	
BF 258	grape	0.2	147	161	162	154	401				560	462	409	435	332	361	390	

Figure 22. Excel format file presenting biomass production for the farm of interest.

3.2.4 VitiGEOSS application layout

The VitiGEOSS application will use the same frame of FieldLook to organise the components of the different intelligent service providers. This will facilitate the implementation of the features designed and used in FieldLook to present the variables of the intelligent services. The application will adopt the colours defined in the project and logos in order to give the identity of VitiGEOSS, which is in line with the communication material and website designed for the project. Figure 23 presents a layout for the map analysis of general units.

Figure 23. General page of map analysis.

4. Following steps

The migration of FieldLook will be completed and evolve in the VitiGEOSS application. The VitiGEOSS application will adopt the layout of VitiGEOSS, this includes colours defined for the project and logos. This new image will be in line with the project image and make of the application a commercial and familiar tool for farmers to increase the marketable potential of VitiGEOSS.

Data concepts and models used in FieldLook and VISCA and concepts used by UNINA combined with the semantic interoperability by Eurecat resulted in a well-defined set of attributes describing each of the management units provided in this project. Esri shape file format was adopted for the boundaries of the management unit. The definition of phenological phases is adopted from VISCA and the definition of key crop indicators is adopted from FieldLook. The weather data follow NCEP convention. The implementation of the standards already defined and to be defined will be further detailed, in an agile approach, during the implementation of the services APIs in the API Service Store and configuration of the services in the VitiGEOSS application.

The API Service Store is successfully tested among the intelligent service providers. All partners APIs are published and accepted in the API Service Store. Following steps will be the setting up the data services in collaboration with partners. Each data service will be discussed with the responsible intelligent service provider to configurate details of the service, details for authentications and authorisation of the data, test data outputs and finalise the standards for the service to be used in VitiGEOSS.

Access to the FieldLook sandbox have been requested and will be granted to end-users for the visualisation of key crop indicators for the different sites in Spain, Portugal and Italy. A test of the application will be organised with the end-users in order to receive their feedback and report issues to the development team in charge of the application.

A co-development approach will include the interaction of eLEAF with intelligent service providers to implement the mock-ups defined for each of the services, discuss the feasibility of the features proposed in the use case functionalities and visualise the data through the VitiGEOSS application. End-users will play a pivotal role in this co-development as they will decide on the final integration and visualisation on the data with the application. This will be carried out during dedicated sessions between intelligent service providers, end-users and eLEAF.

A test scheme will be designed to plan repeatable tests which will show how the system meets the requirements set out in the use case scenarios description (D3.1). Once the interaction of the intelligent services has started, the tests will be planned and run by consortium partners and the results recorded and presented in the respective reports for verifying the results of the results and readiness of the service.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] VitiGEOSS D3.9, “System architecture blueprint”, February 2021
- [2] VitiGEOSS D3.1, “Report on use case scenarios descriptions”, June 2021

